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Abstract:

Teaching is often considered to be the noblest profession among all professions. The definition and parameter of professional ethics varies from society to society and from time to time. With change in social setup, pattern and dimension of society the ethics also change. Without high standards of Professional ethics teaching could never be regarded as full-fledged profession. Code of Professional Ethics for school teachers is an attempt to provide direction and guidance to the teachers in enhancing the dignity of their professional work. The Code of Professional Ethics for teachers provides a framework Present scenario of teaching profession is now at very low ebb. Some of the teachers are found to indulge in all sorts of malpractices and self-centered. Values have fallen and they are trampled under the brutal boots of the reckless teaching community. Professional ethics lie not in laws and government but in the honesty and moral responsibility of the teacher. Teachers should create a peaceful climate in educational institutions; they can play a pivotal role in removing social, caste, communal, religious and barriers that threaten the very existence of the nation. The educator recognizes the magnitude of the responsibility inherent in the teaching process. The desire for the respect and confidence of one's colleagues, of students, of parents, and of the members of the community provides the incentive to attain and maintain the highest possible degree of ethical conduct. The Code of Ethics of the Education Profession indicates the aspiration of all educators and provides standards by which to judge conduct. The educator, believing in the worth and dignity of each human being, recognizes the supreme importance of the pursuit of truth, devotion to excellence, and the nurture of democratic principles. Essential to these goals is the protection of freedom to learn and to teach and the guarantee of equal educational opportunity for all.

Introduction:

The education profession is vested by the public with a trust and responsibility requiring the highest ideals of professional service. In the belief that the quality of the services of the education profession directly influences the nation and its citizens, the educator shall exert every effort to raise professional standards, to promote a climate that encourages the exercise of professional judgment, to achieve conditions that attract persons worthy of the trust to careers in education, and to assist in preventing the practice of the profession by unqualified persons.

Objectives of Teaching Profession:

In 2001, Education International (EI), officially entered this debate when the Declaration on Professional Ethics (DPE) was adopted by EI's 3rd World Congress held in Jomtien, Thailand. The document was further updated at its 4th World Congress in Porto Alegre, Brazil in 2004.

Its Objectives Are:

- to raise consciousness about the norms and ethics of the teaching profession;
- to help increase job satisfaction in education; to enhance status and self-esteem, and to increase respect for the profession in communities, parents, colleagues and community.

According to the code of ethics, All Utkal Primary Teachers Federation (AUPTF) the main duty of teachers lies towards the well-being of students. It stresses that teachers must treat all children equally irrespective of their caste, religion, gender and class. It specifically cautioned teachers against subjecting any child to fear, trauma, anxiety, and physical punishment. Like other professional bodies, AUPTF also recommends stringent action against teachers, who violate the codes. Orissa is the first state in the country where such a code of conduct is issued for teachers, though the proposal is pending with a national-level organization for the last few years. The main aim is to bring discipline and professionalism among teachers," said general secretary of AUPTF, Kamalakanta, and Tripathy.

Teacher's Role

Teachers should play a more dynamic part in cultivating a sense of international understanding. The teacher should have a faith in a world society and imbibe the spirit among his pupils through effective teaching and encouraging international activities. It could be stated that "Education for international understanding and cooperation is something that cannot be pursued in vacuum, but that must pervade the whole school life and learning".

Teacher's Personal Values:

The society expects that the teacher should be a role model in virtues for students to imbibe. A teacher is felicitated more often for his good conduct .than his scholarship. The following are the important values which every teacher is expected to follow in his personal life:

- Adhering to truth
- Exhibiting good habits
- Simplicity and cleanliness
- Punctuality
- Acting without any bias
- Avoiding aggressive language and violent acts
- Be duty conscious
- Not talking ill of others, particularly in their absence
- Cooperating with other teachers
- Helping the poor and needy.

The educator, believing in the worth and dignity of each human being, recognizes the supreme importance of the pursuit of truth, devotion to excellence, and the nurture of democratic principles. Essential to these goals is the protection of freedom to learn and to teach and the guarantee of equal educational opportunity for all. The educator accepts the responsibility to adhere to the highest ethical standards. The educator recognizes the magnitude of the responsibility inherent in the teaching process. The desire for the respect and confidence of one's colleagues, of students, of parents, and of the members of the community provides the incentive to attain and maintain the highest possible degree of ethical conduct. The Code of Ethics of the Education Profession indicates the aspiration of all educators and provides standards by which to judge conduct. The remedies specified by the NEA affiliates for the violation of any provision of this Code shall be exclusive and no such provision shall be enforceable in any form other than one specifically designed by the NEA or its affiliates.

Need for Professional Ethics for Teachers:

For Self-Correction:

Man and his thinking keep changing. It is human to tend towards comfort, selfishness, laziness and money. It is difficult to follow and abide by truth, hard work, simple living and honesty etc., As a result, an individual turns towards the easier ways of life without thinking what effect it will have on him, his family, profession and society. Man slowly turns selfish and extent. Professional ethics correct us if we do wrong or intend to do wrong.

For Self-Satisfaction:

Self-satisfaction is more related to our inner self and our feelings. when we follow the ethical code of society and profession we are regarded as hard working, honest, dutiful, righteous etc., all this makes us more respectable and more prominent than others. Whenever anyone is acknowledged for a right job, he starts governing respect and liking; all this gives self-satisfaction. Professional ethics enable a person to judge himself and decide and not accept what others decide for him.

To Shape the Personality:

Professional ethics in teaching profession emphasize the teacher to follow pre-established norms in his thought and in actions, even in one's dressing up, speaking etiquettes etc.,; by following similar ethics, the personality of an individual is reshaped and he becomes a teacher in real sense.

To Set Up Ideal for Students:

If a teacher behaves in a very positive and appropriate manner, the students follow him and want to become like him and want o become like him. Hence by behaving in an ethical manner the teacher becomes an ideal for student.

Improvement of Human Relations:

Professional ethics guide the teachers to keep in mind the social betterment, respect for others brotherhood, tolerance, cooperation etc. An individual who is guided by professional ethics helps others to maximum; by doing so he develops positive feelings, which improve human relations. When human relations improve the school becomes the best place for teachers, students and parents to work and coordinate. All this ultimately gives results and improves overall standards.

Development of Society:

If the professional ethics are forgotten the individual as well the society starts moving in a wrong direction. By following professional ethics the teacher takes the society in the right direction and makes it a better place to live in.

Professional Excellence:

The work culture is strengthened when the professionals of the profession act and interact professionally in a ethical manner.

To improve the Professional Environment:

Professional environment includes the people, infrastructure, working conditions and working hours. Professional ethics ensure that due place and respect are given to the seniors, to the higher authorities, responsibility and working hours. When the teachers follow such ethical codes of a teaching profession the environment remains calm, congenial and relaxed for effective working.

To Follow the Norms and Principles of the Profession:

Professional ethics binds the teachers to their job and help them to differentiate between Professional development and self interest. They include extra responsibility, which we have to shoulder from time to time. Professional ethics are self-binding for better professional output. They should be mainly regarded as self-directing and self-disciplining rules and conduct which help not only in imparting the role of teachers but also in promoting excellence in teaching.

Present Scenario of Teaching Profession:

Another difference between the past and present tasks of teachers is represented by the technical background they need to be able to use and handle effectively (computer, photocopier, power point, projectors, etc). Instead of teaching chalk face, they need to be an information technology expert, a technician or/and a photocopy master.

One of the biggest challenges for teachers is that their role in the school management has also changed. The school needs them as individuals, who can make decisions and cope with the stress of the changing world of schools. At the same time teachers need to be able to work in teams, co-operate with colleagues and parents, they have to write projects to gain money for the school programmes, they have to be PR experts and need to do all these things for a modest monthly income.

Teachers once to be a noble profession are now at very low ebb. Some of the teachers found to indulge in all sorts of malpractice and are self-cantered. They are found to spend most of their leisure time in other activities. They are highly politicized and ridicule those teachers who do good work. Some of them are found to even en cash their calibre. Values have fallen and they are trampled under the brutal boots of the reckless teaching community. This is particularly rampart in developing nations and underdeveloped nations. An enormous effort is required to reverse this trend. Various measures have to be spelled out clearly to improve the personalities of the teachers. Offenders should be dealt with severe disciplinary action. Value education, therefore, should occupy a significant position in the academic curriculum. Value education can promote professional ethics in teachers. Hence, professional ethics should be a compulsory component of value education in teacher education programme.

Conclusion:

A Teacher is always a student; a seeker of knowledge. A teacher is not merely a teacher but he is a more effective demonstrator through his personal life of values, attitude, outlook, behaviour and performance. By following professional ethics, the teachers conduct and behaviour become respectable and socially acceptable. If a teacher behaves in a very positive and appropriate manner, the students follow him and want to become like him. Hence, by following professional ethics, a teacher becomes the ideal for students. If the professional ethics are forgotten, the individual as well as the society in the right direction and makes it a better place to live in. Professional ethics is a means of developing attitude conducive to responsible citizenship and to more orderly personal living. Professional ethics lie not in laws and government but in the honesty and moral responsibility of the teacher.

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